

www.arseam.com

MINIMIZING MESSAGE DELAY UNDER JAMMING BASED ON CAMOUFLAGE TRAFFIC FOR SMARTGRID APPLICATIONS

Muhammed Siyad P.S¹, Sreelakshmi K Sunil², Abdul Rahim K.A³,
Uba Balan.P⁴ Shejina N.M⁵

^{1,2,3,4} UG Students, Department of Computer Science and Engineering,

⁵ Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering,
IES College of Engineering, Chittilappilly, Thrissur.

Abstract:

Objective- The use of wireless network introduces potential security vulnerabilities due to the shared nature of wireless channels. Indeed, it has been pointed out in that the jamming attack, which uses radio interference to disrupt wireless communications, can result in network performance degradation and even denial-of-service in power applications, thereby being a primary security threat to prevent the deployment of wireless networks for the smart grid. To address this issue by considering a wireless network that uses multiple frequency and code channels to provide jamming resilience for smart grid applications.

Design / Methodology/ Approach- Java is used for building front end and My SQL for the back end. Here the operating system is Windows or Linux. Net Beans is used for IDE.

Findings- Wireless networks have become an essential integration to the communication infrastructure for the smart grid. There have been extensive works on designing spread spectrum based communication schemes, which provide jamming resilience to conventional wireless networks by using multiple orthogonal frequency or code channels. We address this issue by considering a wireless network that uses multiple frequency and code channels to provide jamming resilience for smart grid applications. We consider two general jamming-resilient communication modes for smart grid applications: coordinated and uncoordinated modes. . In coordinated mode, the sender and receiver share a common secret or key, which is unknown to attackers. Accordingly, an attacker has to choose its own strategy to disrupt the communication

between the transmitter and receiver. Uncoordinated communication is therefore used to help establish such an initial key. In uncoordinated communication, the sender and receiver randomly choose a frequency-code channel to transmit and receive, respectively.

Limitations- Provide high data security, so that there will not be any data loss. But no safety requirements have been identified and it has to be taken into consideration.

Practical implications- This paper is very helpful for the minimizing the message delay under jamming.

Originality/Value- It will help in improving the efficiency for the delay performance guarantee for smart grid under any jamming attack.

Keywords: Smart grid, Camouflage, MANET, EAACK, HLA

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 OVERVIEW

SMART grid is an emerging cyber-physical system that incorporates networked control mechanisms in to conventional power infrastructure. To facilitate information delivery for such mechanisms, wireless networks that provide flexible and untethered network access have been proposed and designed for a variety of smart grid applications, such as substation automation and home metering. As a result, wireless networks have become an essential integration to the communication infrastructure for the smart grid. There have been extensive works on designing spread spectrum based communication schemes, which provide jamming resilience to conventional wireless networks by using multiple orthogonal frequency or code channels. An open question is how to minimize message delay for smart grid communication under any potential jamming attack .To facilitates efficient information exchange, wireless network have been proposed smart grid. The jamming attack that constantly broadcast radio interference is a primary security threat to prevent the deployment of wireless network in the smart grid .We aim at solving a fundamental yet open question for wireless smart grid applications: how to minimize the message delay under worst case jamming attacks. The answer to this question cannot only help us design network strategies against worst-case jamming attacks in wireless smart grid

applications, but also offer general guidance into jamming defense strategies in cyber-physical systems. We address this issue by considering a wireless network that uses multiple frequency and code channels to provide jamming resilience for smart grid applications. We consider two general jamming-resilient communication modes for smart grid applications: coordinated and uncoordinated modes. In coordinated mode, the sender and receiver share a common secret or key, which is unknown to attackers. Accordingly, an attacker has to choose its own strategy to disrupt the communication between the transmitter and receiver. Uncoordinated communication is therefore used to help establish such an initial key. In uncoordinated communication, the sender and receiver randomly choose a frequency-code channel to transmit and receive, respectively. A message can be delivered from the sender to the receiver only if they both reside at the same channel, and at the same time the jammer does not disrupt the transmission on the channel. The proposing system can enhance the delay performance guarantee for smart grid application under any attack.

II. RELATED WORKS

2.1. Eaack-A secure intrusion detection and prevention system for MANETS:

Wireless networks are been used now-a-days. The most important fact about wireless network is it is mobile. It is thus used in many fields. One of the most important applications of wireless networks is Mobile Ad hoc network (MANET) in which all the nodes work as both transmitter and receiver. MANETs are used in various fields like military, industry and emergency recovery. So it is important to have a first-hand knowledge about MANETs. But there is a certain drawback in MANETs, that it becomes prone to malicious attacks very fast. To avoid such attacks a good intrusion detection and prevention system is needed. This paper proposed a system which can detect as well as prevent the malicious attacks. The system is named as Enhanced Adaptive acknowledgment (EAACK). EAACK gives a better malicious behavior-detection than the traditional approaches.

2.2 Privacy-preserving and truthful detection of packet dropping attacks in wireless Ad hoc networks:

Link error and malicious packet dropping are two sources for packet losses in multi-hop wireless ad hoc network. While observing a sequence of packet losses in the network, the interest in this paper is that determining whether the losses are caused by link errors only, or by the combined effect of link errors and malicious drop. In this paper, it is especially interested in the insider-attack case, whereby malicious nodes that are part of the route exploit their knowledge of the communication context to selectively drop a small amount of packets critical to the network performance. Because the packet dropping rate in this case is comparable to the channel error rate, conventional algorithms that are based on detecting the packet loss rate cannot achieve satisfactory detection accuracy. To improve the detection accuracy, they propose to exploit the correlations between lost packets. Furthermore, to ensure truthful calculation of these correlations, develop a homomorphic linear authenticator (HLA) based public auditing architecture that allows the detector to verify the truthfulness of the packet loss information reported by nodes. This construction is privacy preserving, collusion proof, and incurs low communication and storage overheads. To reduce the computation overhead of the baseline scheme, a packet-block-based mechanism is also proposed, which allows one to trade detection accuracy for lower computation complexity. Through extensive simulations, here verify that the proposed mechanisms achieve significantly better detection accuracy than conventional methods such as a maximum-likelihood based detection.

2.3 IEC 61850 communication networks and system in substations:

Over the last decade, the “digitization” of the electron enterprise has grown at exponential rates. Utility, industrial, commercial, and even residential consumers are transforming all aspects of their lives into the digital domain. Moving forward, it is expected that every piece of equipment, every receptacle, every switch, and even every light bulb will possess some type of setting, monitoring and or control. In order to be able to manage the large number of devices and to enable the various devices to communicate with one another, a new communication model was needed. That model has been developed and standardized as IEC 61850 – Communication Networks and Systems in Substations. This paper looks at the needs of

next generation communication systems and provides an overview of the IEC 61850 protocol and how it meets these needs. Communication has always played a critical role in the real-time operation of the power system in the beginning, the telephone was used to communicate line loadings back to the control centre as well as to dispatch operators to perform switching operations at substations. A key component of a communication system is the ability to describe themselves from both a data and services (communication functions that an IED performs) perspective.

I. 2.4 The feasibility of launching and detecting jamming attacks in wireless networks:

Wireless networks are built upon a shared medium that makes it easy for adversaries to launch jamming-style attacks. These attacks can be easily accomplished by an adversary emitting radio frequency signals that do not follow an underlying MAC protocol. First analysing the problem of conducting radio interference attacks on wireless networks, and second examining the critical issue of diagnosing the presence of jamming attacks. Define a jammer to be an entity who is purposefully trying to interfere with the physical transmission and reception of wireless communications.

Following two metrics to measure the effectiveness of a jammer:

Packet Send Ratio (PSR): The ratio of packets that are successfully sent out by a legitimate traffic. Source compared to the number of packets it intends to send out at the MAC layer. Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR): The ratio of pack- est. that are successfully delivered to a destination compared to the number of packets that have been sent out by the sender. Then include the type of jammers.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

We address this issue by considering a wireless network that uses multiple frequencies and code channels to provide jamming resilience for smart grid applications. We consider two general jamming resilience for smart grid applications : coordinated and uncoordinated modes. In coordinated modes the sender and receiver share a common secret or key which is unknown to attackers, accordingly an attacker has to choose its own strategy to disrupt the communication

between the transmitter and the receiver. Coordinated communication is conventional model spread spectrum system. However, the transmitter and receiver may not share a common secret initially (e.g. a node joins a network and attempt to establish a secret with others). Uncoordinated communication is there for use to help establish such an initial key. The sender and receiver randomly choose a frequency code channels to transmit and receive respectively.

Fig 1: Initial setting

Fig 2: File transfer

Here the figure 1 and figure 2 describe the Architecture diagram for the proposed model. In figure 1 gives the idea about the initial settings. This is our initialization process in which we configure the nodes and route. Initially the admin will add the nodes and then configure them to create routes. During this time the node details and route details are stored in the DB. In figure 2 gives the idea about file transfer. User is acting as the sender and receiver. When a user sends a message he will become the sender and who receiving the message will be the receiver. Sender can select a particular route and send messages to receiver through that route. There may exist several routes from sender to receiver. All the sending details will store in the database. By applying traffic to the route we will implement that we can minimize the message delay.

IV. CONCLUSION

Here we provided a comprehensive study on minimizing message delay for smart grid applications under jamming attacks. By defining a generic jamming process, we showed that the worst-case message delay is a U-shaped function of network traffic load. We designed a distributed method, TACT, to generate camouflage traffic to balance the network load at the optimal point. TACT achieved nearly-optimal performance. It is challenging to design an adaptive method that always works at the optimal load. The concept of transmitting camouflage traffic can lead to more TACT-like methods to further improve the delay performance for wireless smart grid applications. We showed that TACT is a promising method to significantly improves the delay performance in the smart grid under jamming attacks.

V. REFERENCES

- [1] AusCERT. AA-2004.02 - denial of service vulnerability in IEEE 802.11 wireless devices. <http://www.auscert.org>.
- [2] C. Ateniese, R. Burns, R. Curtmola, J. Herring, L. Kissner, Z. Peterson, and D. Song, "Provable data possession at untrusted stores," in Proc. ACM Conf. Comput. and Commun. Secur., Oct. 2007, pp. 598–610.

- [3] EC 61850-Communication Networks and Systems in Substations; <http://domino.iec.ch/webstore/webstore.nsf/searchview/?SearchView=&SearchOrder=4&SearchWV=TRUE&SearchMax=1000&Query=61850&submit=OK>
- [4] F. Cleveland, “Uses of wireless communications to enhance power system reliability,” in Proc. IEEE Power Eng. Soc. Gen. Meeting, Jun. 2007, p. 1.
- [5] Guidelines for Smart Grid Cyber Security, NIST IR-7628, NIST Smart Grid Cyber Security Working Group, vol. 1-3, Aug. 2010.
- [6] IEEE Std 802.11i/d3.0. Available at <http://www.cs.umd.edu/mhshin/doc/802.11/802.11i-D3.0.pdf>.
- [7] J. N. Arauz, “802.11 Markov channel modeling,” Ph.D. dissertation, School Inform. Sci., Univ. Pittsburgh, Pittsburgh, PA, USA, 2004.
- [8] K. Al Agha, M.-H. Bertin, T. Dang, A. Guitton, P. Minet, T. Val, and J.-B. Viollet, “Which wireless technology for industrial wireless sensor networks? The development of OCARI technol,” *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 56, no. 10, pp. 4266–4278, Oct. 2009.
- [9] Manufacturing Messaging Specification; ISO 9506-1&2:2003; Part 1 – Service Definition: Part 2 – Protocol Specification
- [10] P. M. Kanabar, M. G. Kanabar, W. El-Khattam, T. S. Sidhu, and A. Shami, “Evaluation of communication technologies for IEC 61850 based distribution automation system with distributed energy resources,” in Proc. IEEE Power Eng. Soc. Gen. Meet., 2009, pp. 1–8.
- [11] R. Akbani, T. Korkmaz, and G. V. S. Raju, “Mobile Ad hoc Network Security,” in *Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering*, vol. 127. New York: Springer-Verlag, 2012, pp. 659–666.